

**THE CURRENT STATE OF EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES
IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF
UZBEKISTAN**

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Annotation: This article aims to improve the quality of educational services, increase the competitiveness of higher education organizations, the main characteristics of state higher education organizations, develop new directions of management in higher education organizations, prepare recommendations for them and put them into practice.

Key words: higher education, management, state, non-state, educational service, quality, strategic planning, external environment, internal environment, organization, competition, expert.

In the country's economy, economic development is observed as a result of the emergence of new innovations through the expansion of the production of educational services, scientific and technical products, educational and methodological products, as a result of the activities of higher educational institutions.

In addition, universities carry out scientific, administrative, economic, human resources and financial activities. When it comes to professors and teachers of public and private higher education institutions, it is worth noting that many teachers of public universities seek to work in private institutions of higher education on an hourly or part-time basis. At the same time, this situation does not affect the quality of educational services, because work motivation in non-state higher educational institutions is higher than in state universities. Undoubtedly, educational services are

the main activity of universities, their mission. However, the mission of higher education institutions will not be successful without involving teachers in scientific research and experimental construction work.

The results of scientific and research work are introduced into the educational process, ensuring high quality of service and extension of its life cycle. Improving the quality of educational services is the most important factor in increasing the competitiveness of higher education organizations. In the development of the state policy in the field of higher education, it is necessary to take into account the changes in the education market, today, along with the state higher education organizations, private higher education organizations are also allowed to operate. This, in turn, will increase the competition between educational organizations and increase the efficiency of higher education activities, it will be necessary for them to have a clear understanding of the quality of education in the field of "Educational Services".

Educational services have a number of specific features that distinguish them from other services, for example, legal, auditing services. At the same time, educational services mean the amount of educational and scientific information, the sum total of general education and knowledge. At the same time, educational services have a number of common features with other services provided by related organizations, namely low level of sensitivity, inseparability of educational services from the source, impossibility of storage and transportation, quality inconsistency. Particular attention should be paid to the inseparability of the educational service from its source (scientific and pedagogical personnel, scientific and educational potential, material and technical base and financial resources of the university). Let's also explain the concept of "quality inconsistency". This concept is related to the fact that the quality of service determines the accumulated scientific and educational potential of the university. This can be explained by the fact that the level of training of students in the same specialty in different higher educational institutions is not the same. The specific nature of the educational activity makes it difficult to evaluate the consumer characteristics of the provided services.

Some ideas about the quality of services can be obtained by conducting a sociological survey of alumni who have used the services of a particular university. By providing educational services, the university can interact with the state (meeting the needs of society by ordering highly qualified workers in exchange for financial, material, technical and informational resources). Also, in all higher education institutions, the educational system is functional, each system has its own attributes, and the mission and social responsibility of higher education should be re-focused. After all, higher educational institutions are centers of culture, science, and education, and should serve to form not only professional skills, but also an active life position of future specialists.

The main characteristics of state higher education organizations today are:

First, having a high level of training of specialists using effective educational technologies;

Secondly, the unity of educational and research activities, the existence of classical university specialties, the existence of integration of education, science and culture in the country and region;

Thirdly, the existence of long-term strategies for the formation of scientific potential in state educational organizations, etc.

In recent years, a new direction has been formed in management theory and practice - "management - education", providing knowledge by relying on knowledge transfer, prioritization and methodical techniques;

technocratic type, in which priority is given to the use of technical means of teaching;

flexible type, the essence of which is regular adjustment of training in terms of style, complexity, and methods used.

Олий таълим муассасасида юқори раҳбариятнинг ролини бошқарувда рол it is necessary to emphasize the high level of participation, and in fulfilling obligations of a legal and social nature, in motivating and activating subordinates (organizational employees), in developing external relations and information

sources for mutual communication, in studying the characteristics of the organization of the external environment and external conditions responsible for the actions of the organization, external and in responding to information received from internal sources, including in the form of a "nerve center" in crisis situations, checking external decisions and the organization's reaction, efforts to adapt the organization to the external environment; is manifested in making decisions on the management of organizational resources.

A new direction of management in higher education organizations is a system for monitoring the quality of education, including a system for clarifying and coordinating the interaction of subjects (external and internal) and objects (students, teachers and the educational process itself). It carries out external monitoring by the higher management body of the system through the licensing of higher education institutions, which ensures the right to use educational services in specific specialties. In addition, this body certifies and then accredits higher education institutions. The state control inspectorate is the main obstacle to the provision of poor quality educational services in higher education today.

In the process of accumulation of knowledge, generalization and revision of existing knowledge, society added new elements (concepts, paradigms, concepts) to them. Since HEIs satisfy society's needs for knowledge, specialists for various spheres of life, the management system implements the principle of gathering and technical (information) compatibility of functional space and components and boundaries of management systems of different levels and scales. When performing the classical functions of management in HEIs, it should be taken into account that each society sets new and new requirements for the quality of education in different periods.

The dynamism of this process reflects the development strategy that should be taken into account when planning the university's activities.

In our opinion, strategic planning of university activities should be based on three components:

- taking into account the rules of strategy theory;
- macro and macroeconomic theories;
- theory of systematic modeling of microeconomic processes.

Adaptation of HEIs and their organizational structures to the life environment is dynamic and occurs throughout the life cycle of the university. The activity of the organization is carried out under the influence of the external environment. Differentiate between direct and indirect influence environment.

At the same time, no matter what level of the external environment this or that factor belongs to, four characteristics of environmental factors can be distinguished: interdependence; complexity; mobility; uncertainty. Interdependence of environmental factors is the interaction of various factors in the process of organizational activity. The complexity of the external environment is the number of factors that significantly affect the organization's performance and to which the organization must respond. The mobility of the external environment is the speed at which changes occur in the organization's environment. For example, the environment of modern organizations is changing rapidly. This is a general trend. However, there are organizations whose external environment is particularly dynamic. The uncertainty of the external environment is determined by the amount of information about a certain factor of the organization, as well as confidence in the reliability of this information. Internal environment: people; abilities; needs; expectations; perception; relationships; values; groups; leadership; working conditions etc. The external environment affects the formation of the appropriate stage of the management cycle, as well as the process of organizing the activities of university employees. The great changes taking place in the external environment are related to the increase of the population, the activation of international relations, the acceleration of scientific and technical progress, the renewal of production structures, and the change of lifestyle. These changes are a factor of fundamental changes in the management development system, including education.

The organizational mechanism helps to rationally divide the work in the university, establishing the correspondence between the organizational structure and the list of specific tasks, and becomes the basis for planning and distributing the work. In the implementation of a management function such as "organization", it should be assumed that the end product of the process of providing educational services is a stable system of individuals working together based on a hierarchy of levels and division of labor to achieve these goals. according to the functions in which general goals are realized, organizations are divided into production, which is engaged in the creation of goods, services, capital; support; flexible; political organizations. Organizations of the first type ensure the material existence of society.

The purpose of organizational support is to socialize individuals to fulfill their appropriate roles in the organization or society. This type of organization includes schools, universities, etc. Adaptive organizations create knowledge, develop and test theories (universities, research organizations). Their task is to provide society with information and integration. Political organizations are the main sources of power.

A number of stages can be distinguished in the technology of forming organizations:

- a group of people understands the needs of society and develops solutions for their implementation ("crystallization");
- people forming the organization begin to interact with other organizations about their goals and joint efforts, recognition ("recognition");
- the activity of the organization begins to be implemented on the basis of stable forms of interaction of its members with other organizations ("institutionalization").

The following components of the external environment are distinguished: economic conditions, competitors, consumers, legislation, value system, public opinion. The external environment of HEIs is dynamic and is made more complex by its diversity. First of all, the number of communications is increasing, their

resource base is changing. The internal environment reflects the interdependence of university components (parts, subsystems, functions). The internal environment affects the characteristics and functions of the system (the state of the organization, its forms, restrictions and variables in internal actions). Internal variables are situational factors created by people working within the organization and as a result of management decisions (controllable and uncontrollable). These decisions affect the state of the organization, causing the need to correct them (goals, structure, tasks, technologies, people).

REFERENCES

1. Bulturbayevich, M. B., Saodat, S., Umida, J., Shakhnoza, N., & Feruza, S. Theoretical and Practical Bases of Investments and Processes of Their Distribution in the Conditions of Modernization of Economy. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(9), 132-137.
2. Bulturbayevich, M. B., Saodat, S., Umida, J., Shakhnoza, N., & Feruza, S. (2020). Mechanisms of State Incentives for Logistics Centers to Ensure the Competitiveness of the Economy. *International Engineering Journal For Research & Development*, 5(5), 7.
3. Bulturbayevich, M. B. (2022). TAXES AND THEIR TRANSFER. LOSS OF" DEAD" CARGO WHEN TAXED. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429*, 11(05), 22-31.
4. Bulturbayevich, M. B. (2022). IN PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP EMPLOYEE INCENTIVES ISSUES. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603*, 11(04), 21-27.
5. Bulturbayevich, M. B. (2021). Challenges of Digital Educational Environment. *Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability*, 4, 54-60.

6. Bulturbayevich, M. B. (2021). Development Of Innovative Activities Of Enterprises On The Basis Of Vertical Integration Processes. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, 12(10), 5020-5031.

7. Bulturbayevich, M. B. (2021). CHALLENGES IN DEVELOPING A DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT. *Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability*, 2, 1-9.

8. Bulturbayevich, M. B. (2021, February). IMPROVING THE MECHANISMS OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF INNOVATION PROCESSES IN ENTERPRISES. In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 15, No. 1, pp. 130-136).

9. Bulturbayevich, M. B. (2021). CHALLENGES IN DEVELOPING A DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT. *Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability*, 2, 1-9.

10. Bulturbayevich, M. B. (2021, February). IMPROVING THE MECHANISMS OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF INNOVATION PROCESSES IN ENTERPRISES. In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 15, No. 1, pp. 130-136).

11. Bulturbayevich, M. B. (2020). Management of innovation processes- An important factor for increasing the competitiveness of enterprises. *European Journal of Molecular and Clinical Medicine*, 7(7), 712-719.

12. Mullabayev, B. B. (2020). Theoretical and Methodological Bases of Assessment of Innovative Potential of Industrial Enterprises. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies (IJPSAT)*, 22, 11-18.

13. Mullabaev, B. B. (2018). Econometric Analysis Of Vertical Integration Of The Light Industry Enterprises Of The Namangan Region (On The Example Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan). *Scientific Review: Theory and Practice*, (8), 22, 36.

14. Mullabayev, B. B. (2018). Economic analysis of vertical integration integration of the Namangan region (on the prerogative of the Republic of Uzbekistan). *Science of theory: theory and practice*"-8.

15. Bulturbayevich, M. B. (2022). THE ROLE OF SMALL BUSINESS ENTITIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 16(11), 17-22.

16. Bulturbayevich, M. B., & Botir, G. (2022). THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(09), 44-47.